

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 DOMAIN INTRODUCTION

Big Data is high-volume, high-velocity and/or high-variety information assets that demand cost-effective, innovative forms of information processing that enable enhanced insight, decision making, and process automation. Big Data refers to all data that is being generated across the globe at an unprecedented rate. This data could be either structured or unstructured. Four V's of Big Data are Volume, Velocity, Veracity and Variety.

Volume: The amount of data that businesses can collect is really enormous and hence the volume of the data becomes a critical factor in Big Data analytic.

Velocity: The rate at which new data is being generated all thanks to our independence on the internet, sensors, and machine-to-machine data is also important to parse Big Data in timely manner.

Variety: The data that is generated is completely heterogeneous in the sense that it could be in various formats like video, text, database, numeric, sensor data and so on and hence understanding the type of Big Data is a key factor to unlocking its value.

Veracity: Knowing whether the data that is available is coming from a credible source is utmost important before deciphering and implementing Big Data for business needs.

There is a need to convert Big Data into business intelligence that enterprise can readily deploy.

1.2 PROBLEM DESCRIPTION

With rapid innovations and surge of internet companies like Google, Yahoo, Amazon, eBay and a rapidly growing internet savvy population, today's advanced systems and enterprises are generating data in a very huge volume with great velocity and in a multi-structured formats including videos, images, sensor data, weblogs etc. from different sources. This has given birth to a new type of data called Big Data which is unstructured sometimes semi structured and also unpredictable in nature. This data is mostly generated in real time from social media websites which are increasing exponentially on a daily basis. According to Wikipedia, "Big Data is a term for data sets that are so large or complex that traditional data processing applications are inadequate to deal with them.

1.3 PROJECT DESCRIPTION

In the proposed system, in order to reduce storage space, HDFS concepts are used, and to reduce computational complexities, Bayesian algorithm is used. The goal is to make a simpler climate model people can use which gives the same accuracy as that of a huge climate model. This project explored domains that could benefit from weather forecasting using Big Data analytics and also we explored the challenges which we have to face while taking advantage of weather forecasting. With Bayesian algorithm, the accuracy of prediction is higher when compared to existing algorithm. In order to predict the best outcome, inference mechanism is used for training and testing the system. Bayesian algorithm requires short computation time for training and improves the classification, by removing irrelevant features and providing good performance and accurate predictions.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE SURVEY

Paper 1: Big Data and machine learning for applied Weather forecasts

Authors: Sue Ellen Haupt and Branko Kosovic

Year: 2015

Description:

To blend growing amounts of renewable energy into utility grids requires accurate estimates of the power from those resources for both day ahead planning and real-time operations. This requires predicting the wind and solar resource on those timescales. Accurate prediction of these meteorological variables is a big data problem that requires a multitude of disparate data, multiple models that are each applicable to a specific time frame, and application of computational intelligence techniques to successfully blend all of the model and observational information in real-time and deliver it to the decision-makers at utilities and grid operators. Current weather prediction efforts are an important real time challenge and many applications rely on its accuracy, including aviation safety, defence planning, energy applications and beyond. Considering that the capacity of weather data continues to grow an additional challenge includes selecting and archiving data for continuous retraining of machine learning algorithms.

Paper 2: Classification and Forecasting of Weather using ANN, k-NN and Naïve Bayes Algorithms

Authors: Nishchala C. Barde, Mrunalinee Patole

Year: 2014

Description:

Weather forecasting is a way to predict future weather. It is widely researched area due to the fact that human life on earth is affected by the global climate. In this paper, we have proposed a comparative study between various techniques for prediction. This work focuses on developing an optimized system model which predicts future weather. The frequency of natural hazards occurring due to unpredictable weather conditions have been seen to be increasing causing damage to human life. There are some models that predict weather during real time, or monthly or annual period. This paper presents a system that carries out weather prediction using previous or historical weather data having attributes (Date, Temperature, Humidity, Wind Chill (WC) and Pressure. Various data mining techniques are used for this purpose of weather forecasting such as Multi-layer Perceptron, K-Nearest Neighbour and naive Bayes. Comparison based on evaluation parameters identify which model has more accurately performed the predictions.

Paper 3: An Efficient Algorithm for Mining Association Rules using Confident Frequent Item sets

Authors: Basheer Mohamad Al-Maqaleh, Saleem Khalid Shaab

Year: 2013

Description:

Identifying frequent item sets is one of the most important issues faced by the knowledge discovery and data mining community. There have been a number of successful algorithms developed for extracting frequent item sets in very large databases. Frequent item set mining leads to the discovery of associations and correlations among items in large transactional or relational datasets. A problem with such a process is that the solution of interesting patterns has to be performed only on frequent item sets. Pushing constraints in frequent item sets mining can help pruning the search space. In this paper, an efficient algorithm is proposed to integrate confidence measure during the process of mining frequent item sets, which generates confident frequent item sets. Consequently, the suggested algorithm generates strong association rules from these confident frequent item sets. This technique has been implemented and the experimental results show the usefulness and effectiveness of the proposed algorithm.

Paper 4: Comparative Study of K-NN, Naive Bayes and Decision Tree Classification Techniques

Authors: Sayali D. Jadhav, H. P. Channe

Year: 2014

Description:

Classification is a data mining technique used to predict group membership for data instances within a given dataset. It is used for classifying data into different classes by considering some constraints. The problem of data classification has many applications in various fields of data mining. This is because the problem aims at learning the relationship between a set of feature variables and a target variable of interest. Classification is considered as an example of supervised learning as training data associated with class labels is given as input. Classification algorithms have a wide range of applications like Customer Target Marketing, Medical Disease Diagnosis, Social Network Analysis, Credit Card Rating, Artificial Intelligence, and Document Categorization etc. Several major kinds of classification techniques are K-Nearest Neighbour classifier, Naive Bayes, and Decision Trees. This paper focuses on study of various classification techniques, their advantages and disadvantages.

Paper 5: Concept and Analysis of Information Spaces to Improve Prediction-Based Compression

Authors: Ugur Cayoglu, Frank Tristram, Jörg Meyer, Tobias Kerzenmacher, Peter Braesicke and Achim Streit

Year: 2018

Description:

One of the scientific communities that generate the largest amounts of data today are the climate sciences. New climate models enable model integration at unprecedented resolution, simulating decades and centuries of climate change, including many complex interactions in the Earth system, under different scenarios. Nowadays, limited storage space and ever increasing model output is the bigger challenge. For this reason, we investigate prediction-based data compression where data is processed in a predefined sequence. We show that there is a significant dependence of the compression ratio on the chosen traversal method and the underlying spatiotemporal data model and explore possibilities to retrieve this information to improve compression ratios by the concept of Information Spaces (IS), which provides better predictions and more consistent compression ratios. Furthermore, it allows options for consolidation and fine-granular tuning of predictions, which are not possible with many common approaches used today.

CHAPTER 3

SYSTEM ANALYSIS

3.1 EXISTING SYSTEM

In Existing systems, climate prediction leads to more complexity to the massive centres and maintaining dual systems with the lots of intrinsic redundancies to assure this 100% availability on daily basis. Systems dedicated to climate analysis do need to have the solid software that can recover from a component failure, since the runs are so long and that they do need to manage and analyse massive amounts of information's that was produced by a multiyear simulations. In addition to these, volume and variety of environmental data is increasing exponentially, placing great demand on the infrastructure to transport, manage, and store this information thus continued improvement of forecasts and climate models need a lot of numbers of observations, leading to immense output files and consuming vast compute and storage resources.

3.1.1 DRAWBACKS OF EXISTING SYSTEM

- Inaccurate weather forecasts can cause both air and road transport to stall or even completely shut down.
- Weather forecasting algorithms and mathematical model shave become more complex over time, and are able to incorporate a large number of data points when generating a prediction.
- Numerical weather prediction needs large computations for real time operations and cost overrun still exists.
- Because of linear regression algorithm, leads to less accuracy over climate prediction
- The networks of complex tools needed for today's level of forecasting accuracy are difficult to maintain.

3.2 PROPOSED SYSTEM

In the proposed system we provide weather forecasting using big data analytics and we explored the challenges which we have to face while weather forecasting Areas where climate forecasting has shown great changes are business, tourism and sports. With the help of good predictions can save many lives, reduce damage and economic losses from the inevitable natural disasters. With the help of Bayesian algorithm accuracy of prediction is higher when compare to numerical weather prediction models.

3.2.1 ADVANTAGES OF PROPOSED SYSTEM

- Accuracy is higher when compared to the existing systems with the help of Bayesian classifier.
- Because of using HDFS, Replication factor has been achieved.
- Cost overrun should be reduced.
- In order to reduce the large computations map reduce concepts has been implemented to achieve efficiency

3.3 FEASIBILITY STUDY

A Feasibility study is an analysis used in measuring the ability and likelihood to complete a project successfully including all relevant factors. It must account for factors that affect it such as economic, technology, legal and scheduling factors. The crucial purpose of this phase is to find the need and to define the problem that has to be solved. The key considerations are

- ✓ Economic feasibility
- ✓ Technical feasibility
- ✓ Social feasibility
- ✓ Operational feasibility

3.3.1 Economic feasibility

Economic feasibility determines whether the required software is capable of generating financial gains for the organization. Software is said to be economically feasible if it focuses on the issues listed below. Cost incurred on software development to produce long-term gains for the organization is necessary to consider the benefits that can be achieved by developing the software.

3.3.2 Technical Feasibility

Technical feasibility assesses the current resources (such as hardware and software) technology, which are required to accomplish user requirements in the software within the allocated time and budget. As certain the technology chosen for software development has a large number of users so that they can be consulted when problems arise or improvements are required.

3.3.3 Social Feasibility

Social feasibility addresses the effect that the proposed may have on the social system in the project environment. It must be identified that employees in the particular industries may have specific status symbols within the society.

3.3.4 Operational Feasibility

Operational feasibility refers to the measure of solving problems with the help of a new proposed system. It helps in taking advantage of the opportunities and fulfils the requirements as identified during the development of the project.

CHAPTER 4

SYSTEM DESIGN

4.1 System Architecture

System Architecture is a generic discipline to handle objects (existing or to be created) called “systems”, in a way that supports reasoning about the structural properties of these objects. System architecture is a response to the conceptual and practical difficulties of the description and the design of complex systems.

Fig.4.1 System Architecture

4.2 UML Diagram

4.2.1 Use Case Diagram

A use case diagram is a set of scenarios that describes interactions between a user and a system. A use case diagram displays the relationship among the actors and use cases. The two main components of a use case diagram are use cases and actors. An actor is represents a user or another system that will interact with the system modelled. A use case is an external view of the system that represents some action.

Fig.4.2. Use case Diagram

4.2.2 Class Diagram

Class diagram in the UML is a type of static structure diagram that describes the structure of a system's classes, their attributes, operations and the relationships among objects. Private visibility hides information from anything outside the class partition. Public visibility allows all other classes to view the marked information. Protected visibility allows child classes to access information they inherited from a parent class.

Fig.4.3 Class Diagram

4.2.3 Activity Diagram

Activity diagram is another important diagram in UML to describe dynamic aspects of the system. Activity diagram is basically a flow chart to represent the flow from one activity to another activity. The activity can be described as an operation of the system. So the control flow is drawn from one operation to another. This flow can be sequential, branched or concurrent.

Fig.4.4 Activity Diagram

4.2.4 Sequence Diagram

A sequence diagram in UML is a kind of interaction diagram that shows how the processes operate with one another and in what order. Sequence diagrams are typically associated with use case realizations in the logical view of the system under development. Sequence diagrams are sometimes called event diagrams or event scenarios.

Fig.4.5 Sequence Diagram

4.2.5 Collaboration Diagram

Collaboration diagrams belong to a group of UML diagrams called interaction diagrams. Collaboration diagrams, like sequence diagrams, shows how objects interact over the course of time. However, instead of showing the sequence of events by the layout on the diagram, collaboration diagrams shows the sequence by numbering the messages on the diagram. This makes it easier to show how the objects are linked together, buy harder to see the sequence at a glance.

Fig.4.6 Collaboration Diagram

4.3 Data Flow Diagram

Level 0

Level 1

Level 3

CHAPTER 5

SYSTEM REQUIREMENTS

5.1 HARDWARE REQUIREMENTS

The most common set of requirements is defined by any system or the software application is the physical computer resources also known hardware. A hardware requirement list is often accompanied by a hardware compatibility list (HCL), especially in case of operating systems. An HCL lists tested, compatible and sometimes incompatible hardware devices for a particular operating system or application.

System	: Standard i3/i5
Hard disk	: 250 GB or Higher
RAM	: 4 GB

5.2 SOFTWARE REQUIREMENTS

Software requirements is a field within software engineering that deals with establishing the needs of stakeholders that are to be solved by software. A software requirements specification (SRS) is a comprehensive description of the intended purpose and environment for software under development. The SRS fully describes what the software will do and how it will be expected to perform.

Operating System	: Ubuntu
Coding Language	: Java
Tool & IDE	: JDK 1.8, Eclipse.
Framework	: Hadoop

CHAPTER 6

SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION

6.1 SOFTWARE DESCRIPTION

6.1.1 Java

Java is platform independent. Java is an object-oriented programming language developed initially by James Gosling and colleagues at Sun Microsystems. The language, initially called Oak (named after the oak tree outside Gosling's office), was intended to replace C++, although the feature sets well resembles that of objective C.

6.1.1.1 Features of Java

A class is the definition for a segment of code that can contain both data (called attributes) and functions (called methods). Jvm, Jre, Jdk these are all the backbones of java language. When the interpreter executes the class, it looks for a particular method by the name of main, which sound familiar to C programmers. The main method is passed as a parameter an array of strings (similar to the argv[] of C), and is declared as a static method. Java developers knows "write, once, run anywhere".

Features of Java includes:

- Simple
- Multithreading
- High performance
- Platform independent
- Object oriented

6.1.1.2 Java Programming Language

Java programming language is high-level language and support oops basically class and object concept. Java is platform independent, more powerful, secure, high performance, multithreaded programming language. Java is simple because it has rich set of API (Application Protocol Interface) and garbage collector which is always used to collect UN-Referenced (unused) memory location for improving performance of a java program. Java files have extension

.java and java class files have .class extension which are compiled by java compiler.

Fig.6.1 Software Development Process

6.1.1.3 Java Virtual Machine

JVM (Java Virtual Machine) is a software. It is a specification that provides Runtime environment in which java byte code can be executed. JVM mainly performs following operations. Allocating sufficient memory space for the class properties. Provides runtime environment in which java byte codes can be executed. Converting byte code instruction into machine level instruction. JVM is separately available for every Operating system while installing java software so that JVM is platform dependant.

6.2 LIST OF MODULES

- User authentication
- Data uploading
- Pre-processing
- Data clustering
- Bayesian classification
- Report Prediction

6.2.1 USER AUTHENTICATION

Every last client login the page at that point makes the exchange and utilize this application. Validness is confirmation that a message, exchange, or other trade of data is from the source it cases to be from. Enroll and login choice in landing page. Every single client needs to enlist as the new client for login. Client need to fill the all prerequisite for security reason just, so fill the all subtle elements unique points of interest. Every one of the subtle elements spared in various ways. Make new table for every client and spare points of interest in like manner table.

LOGIN:

Fig.6.2 User Authentication

6.2.2 DATA UPLOADING

The readied informational index will store the Hadoop document framework. HDFS occurrences are partitioned into two segments: the name node, which keeps up metadata to track the arrangement of physical information over the Hadoop case and data nodes, which really store the information. The information stacking to the hdfs utilizing HDFS URL way. The transferred information will be kept up by the name hub and information hubs. The informational index traits are kept up in the name hub like record name, measure, get to consent, and so forth. The crude information kept up by the information hubs. The information hub controlled by the name node. The transferred information can't change any qualities in light of the fact that hdfs have compose once perused many time property.

DATASET UPLOAD:

Fig.6.3 Data Uploading

6.2.3 PREPROCESSING

Information pre-processing is an information mining method that includes changing crude information into a reasonable arrangement. True information is frequently inadequate, conflicting, as well as ailing in specific practices or drifts, and is probably going to contain numerous blunders. Information pre-processing is a demonstrated strategy for settling such issues. The transferred information recover from the hdfs. The recovered information going to the Map Reduce calculation and information will be composed into organized configuration. In this procedure have expelling the unusable qualities from the informational indexes. The information diminishment process is lessened portrayal of the information in an information distribution centre.

PREPROCESS:

Fig.6.4 Pre processing

6.2.4 DATA CLUSTERING

To gather those information into those bunches whose climate information class has been as of now characterized. In this way it develops a procedure to anticipate the promoting of the up and coming days. This one procedure gathering the information and ought to be made out of focuses isolated by little separations, in respect to the separations between groups. The information will gathering in light of the value, open, high, low, shut and time. In this bunching will apply the map reduce with Bayesian approach. It give more productive in high volume information bunching process.

CLUSTERING:

Fig.6.5 Data Clustering

6.2.5 BAYESIAN CLASSIFICATION

It is a statistical classifier and probabilistic prediction and it predict class membership probabilities. It is based on Bayes' theorem. Naive Bayesian classifier can compare performance with decision tree and selected network classifiers. The accuracy and speed is good when applied to large databases. It is a Class Conditional Independence. The effect of an attribute value on a given class is independent of the values of other attributes. It simplifies computations. The Bayesian Belief Networks has graphical models, and it will represent dependencies among subsets of attributes.

CLASSIFICATION:

Fig.6.6 Data Classification

6.2.6 PREDICTION

The cluster value will be different ranges. Those values are gathered and compared to each other's. Finally we will get the low and high result based on the calculation. The predicted values will be given the graphical representation graph

PREDICTION:

FIG 6.7:PREDICTION

CHAPTER 7

SYSTEM TESTING

7.1 GENERAL

Testing is performed to identify errors. It is used for quality assurance. Testing is an integral part of the entire development and maintenance process. The goal of the testing during phase is to verify that the specification has been accurately and completely incorporated into the design, as well as to ensure the correctness of the design itself.

For example, the design must not have any logical faults. The fault in the design is detected before coding commences, otherwise the cost of fixing the faults will be considerably higher as reflected. Detection of design faults can be achieved by means of inspection as well as walkthrough.

7.2 TYPES OF TESTING

All field entries must work properly. Pages must be activated from the identified link. The entry screen, messages and response must not be delayed. There are many types of testing tools used for testing the documents for correctness.

7.2.1 UNIT TESTING

Unit testing is conducted to verify the functional performance of each modular component of the software. Unit testing focuses on the smallest unit of the software design (i.e.), the module. The white-box testing techniques were heavily employed for unit testing.

7.2.2 INTEGRATION TESTING

Integration testing is a systematic technique for constructing the program structure while at the same time conducting tests to uncover errors associated with

interfacing i.e., integration testing is the complete testing of the set of modules which makes up the product. The objective is to take untested modules and build a program structure tester should identify critical modules.

7.2.3 FUNCTIONAL TESTING

Functional test cases involved exercising the code with normal input values for which. The expected results were known as well as boundary values and special values, such as logically related inputs, files of identical elements, and empty files. Three types of tests in functional test:

- Performance Test
- Stress Test
- Structure Test

7.2.4 PERFORMANCE TESTING

It determines the amount of execution time spent in various parts of the unit, program throughput, and response time and device utilization by the program unit.

7.2.5 STRESS TESTING

Stress test is those test designed to intentionally break the unit. A great deal can be learned about the strength and limitations of a program by examining the manner in which a program unit breaks.

7.2.6 STRUCTURED TESTING

Structured testing are concerned with exercising the internal logic of a program and traversing particular execution paths. The way in which White-box testing strategy was employed to ensure that the test cases could guarantee that all independent paths within a module have been exercised at least once.

- Exercise all logical decisions on their true or false side.

- Execute all loops at their boundaries and within their operational bounds.
- Exercising internal data structures to assure their validity.
- Checking attributes for their correctness.
- Handling end of the file condition, I/O errors, buffer problems and textual errors in output information.

7.2.7 WHITE BOX TESTING

This testing is also called as Glass box testing. In this testing, by knowing the specific functions that a product has been designed to perform test can be conducted that demonstrate each function is fully operational at the same time searching for errors in each function. It is a test case design method that uses the control structure of the procedural design to derive test cases. Basis path testing is white box testing. Basis path testing:

- Flow graph notation
- Cyclometric complexity
- Deriving test cases
- Graph matrices control
-

7.2.8 BLACK BOX TESTING

In this testing by knowing the internal operation of a product, test can be conducted to ensure that “all gears mesh”, that is the internal operation performs according to specification and all internal components have been adequately exercised. It fundamentally focuses on the functional requirements of the software. The steps involved in black box test case design are:

- Graph based testing methods
- Equivalence partitioning
- Boundary value analysis
- Comparison testing

TEST	TEST REQUIREMENT	ACTION/ INPUT	EXPECTED RESULT	ACTUAL RESULT	PASS/ FAIL
1	User Registration	Name, email, password, confirm password	New user must do Registration and account should be created	User registered successfully and account created	pass
2	User login	Email,password	Existing user must be login and have to enter correct mail and password	User validated and logged in successfully	pass
3	Admin login	Email,password	Admin should give the default Id and password	Admin account is successfully opened and validated successfully	pass
4	Preprocessing	Hdfs connection, Weather Datasets	To do preprocessing,Datasets Should be there in hdfs	Preprocess done and output generated in hdfs	Pass
5	Report Prediction	Click Month prediction and week prediction	Before prediction ,classification and cluster should be done and hdfs connection should be open	Predicted successfully and connection is opened	Pass

TABLE 7.1 Test Case

CHAPTER 8

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

8.2 RESULT

In existing system Data volume and variety are growing at very fast rate and this is becoming a great challenge in weather forecasting; as now difficulty is to mix these data to provide correct forecasts . Since we have tremendous amount of complex data, so transport, storage and management of data is becoming a problem and is also increasing the overheads. Complex too large required to manage this much amount of data, which can cause millions of dollars of overhead. If in case weather forecasting goes wrong it could lead to shut down of many businesses causing severe loss to the economy and society. So if we could understand the nature of these applications and challenges, we can identify the optimal solutions to these challenges and can have more efficient and reliable applications which can save lives, improve quality of life and business, reduce risks and enhance profitability.

CHAPTER 9

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE ENHANCEMEN

9.1 CONCLUSION

our system predicts the climate based on the available data can be mined and utilized by different companies to obtain the climatic prediction .This can be done by using Hadoop concepts in addition to data, places, temperature etc. This can tell the company the accuracy of the climate and be useful in designing in later

9.2 FUTURE ENHANCEMENT

In this project could be the climate analysis project .The current scope of the projects includes analyzing the change in climate pattern including change in temperature, rainfall etc. By identifying/classifying/categorizing the dataset the climate prediction can be done. In future the project can be used to identify the change in weather pattern all over the world using large amount of dataset and it also provides accuracy in climate prediction pattern.

APPENDICES:

A. Sample Code

SAMPLE CODE:

LOGIN CODE:

```
</head>
<body>
<div class="limiter">
<div class="container-login100">
<div class="wrap-login100 p-l-55 p-r-55 p-t-65 p-b-50">
<form class="login100-form validate-form" action="LoginNew"
method="get"> <span class="login100-form-title p-b-33"> Account Login

</span>
<div>
<input class="input100" type="text" name="name" placeholder="Name">
<span class="focus-input100-1"></span>
<span          class="focus-input100-
2"></span> </div>
<div class="wrap-input100 rs1 validate-input" data-validate="Password
is required">
<input class="input100" type="password" name="pass"
placeholder="Password">
<span          class="focus-input100-
1"></span> <span    class="focus-
input100-2"></span> </div>
<div class="container-login100-form-btn m-t-
20"> <button class="login100-form-btn"> Sign in
```

```
</button>
</div>
<div class="text-centre">
<span class="txt1 ">
Create an account?
</span>
<a href="reg.html" class="txt2 hov1 ">
Sign up
</a>
</div>
</form>
</div>
</div>
</div>
```

PREPROCESSING SERVLET:

```
package server;
import java.io.IOException;
import java.util.ArrayList;
import javax.servlet.ServletException;
import javax.servlet.annotation.WebServlet;
import javax.servlet.http.HttpServlet;
import javax.servlet.http.HttpServletRequest;
import javax.servlet.http.HttpServletResponse;
import javax.servlet.http.HttpSession;
import analyze.Preprocess;
import classify.ClassifyDriver;
import hdfs.ReadPreprocess;
import preprocessing.driverr;
```

```

@WebServlet("/PreprocessServlet")

public class PreprocessServlet extends HttpServlet
{ private static final long serialVersionUID = 1L;

protected void doGet(HttpServletRequest request, HttpServletResponse
response) throws ServletException, IOException {

// TODO Auto-generated method stub

response.getWriter().append("Served at: ").append(request.getContextPath());

}

protected void doPost(HttpServletRequest request, HttpServletResponse
response) throws ServletException, IOException {

    driverr p = new driverr();

    try {
    p.main(null);

    } catch (Exception e)
    {
    System.out.println(e);
    }

    ReadPreprcess read = new ReadPreprcess();
    ArrayList<String> al = read.read();
    HttpSession hs = request.getSession();
    hs.setAttribute("preprocess", al);
    response.sendRedirect("preprocess.jsp");

}

}

```

CLASSIFY SERVLET:

```
package server;
import java.io.IOException;
import java.util.ArrayList;
import javax.servlet.ServletException;
import javax.servlet.annotation.WebServlet;
import javax.servlet.http.HttpServlet;
import javax.servlet.http.HttpServletRequest;
import javax.servlet.http.HttpServletResponse;
import javax.servlet.http.HttpSession;
import analyze.Preprocess;
import hdfs.ClassifyRead;
import hdfs.ReadPreprocess;
/**
 * Servlet implementation class ClassifyServlet
 */
@WebServlet("/ClassifyServlet")
public class ClassifyServlet extends HttpServlet
{ private static final long serialVersionUID =
  1L;
  protected void doGet(HttpServletRequest request, HttpServletResponse
  response) throws ServletException, IOException {
  // TODO Auto-generated method stub
  response.getWriter().append("Served at: ").append(request.getContextPath());
  }
  protected void doPost(HttpServletRequest request, HttpServletResponse
  response) throws ServletException, IOException {
  Preprocess p = new Preprocess();
  try {
  p.main(null);
```

```

} catch (Exception e)
{
System.out.println(e);
// TODO: handle exception
}
ClassifyRead read = new ClassifyRead();
ArrayList<String> al = read.read();
HttpSession hs = request.getSession();
hs.setAttribute("classify", al);
response.sendRedirect("classify.jsp");
}
}

```

REGISTRATION:

```

package login;
import java.io.IOException;
import java.io.PrintWriter;
import java.sql.Connection;
import java.sql.DriverManager;
import java.sql.PreparedStatement;
import javax.servlet.ServletException;
import javax.servlet.annotation.WebServlet;
import javax.servlet.http.HttpServlet;
import javax.servlet.http.HttpServletRequest;
import javax.servlet.http.HttpServletResponse;
import javax.servlet.http.HttpSession;
/**
 * Servlet implementation class RegisterNew
 */
@WebServlet("/RegisterNew")

```

```

public class RegisterNew extends HttpServlet {
private static final long serialVersionUID = 1L;
protected void doGet(HttpServletRequest request, HttpServletResponse
response) throws ServletException, IOException {
// TODO Auto-generated method stub
response.getWriter().append("Served at: ").append(request.getContextPath());
}

protected void doPost(HttpServletRequest request, HttpServletResponse
response) throws ServletException, IOException {
String name = request.getParameter("name");
String email = request.getParameter("email");
String pass = request.getParameter("pass");
String cpass = request.getParameter("re_pass");
PrintWriter out =response.getWriter();
try {
Class.forName("com.mysql.jdbc.Driver");
Connection con =
DriverManager.getConnection("jdbc:mysql://localhost:3306/weather","root","
admin");

PreparedStatement ps = con.prepareStatement("insert into reg
values(?,?,?,?)");
ps.setString(1, name);
ps.setString(2, email);
ps.setString(3, pass);
ps.setString(4, cpass);
int i = ps.executeUpdate();
if(i>0) {
HttpSession session=request.getSession();
session.setAttribute("name", name);
response.sendRedirect("login.html");
}else {

```

```
response.sendRedirect("error.jsp");  
}  
} catch (Exception e)  
{  
System.out.println(e);  
}}}
```

B. Screenshots

HOME:

ADMIN HOME:

REGISTRATION:

PREDICTION:

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